

Proceedings of Abstracts
13th International Conference on

Air Quality Science and Application

Venue:

Aristotle University's Research Dissemination Center (KEDEA)

27 June – 1 July 2022

EDITORS

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ORGANISED BY

University of Hertfordshire, UK and Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece

University of
Hertfordshire **UH**

Published by the Air Quality Conference
College Lane
Hatfield
AL10 9AB
United Kingdom

ISBN: 978-1-3999-2835-9

DOI: 10.18745/PB.25560

Suggested citation:

Authors..... (2022). *Proceedings of Abstracts 13th International Conference on Air Quality: Science and Application*. Published by Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece and University of Hertfordshire, UK, pp XX, <https://doi.org/10.18745/PB.25560>

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Production:

Laboratory of Heat Transfer and Environmental Engineering
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
Thessaloniki
Greece

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IMPACT OF METEOROLOGICAL CONDITIONS ON AMBIENT FINE PARTICULATE MATTER (PM_{2.5}) IN THE CITY OF NOVI SAD, SERBIA

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Summary

In order to examine the impact of meteorological conditions on ambient PM_{2.5} concentrations in the City of Novi Sad, Serbia, we used monitoring data of air temperature, air humidity and wind speed by Republic of Hydrometeorology Service of Serbia during 2017, as well as daily concentration of PM_{2.5} from two monitoring stations (urban traffic and urban background). The main results of univariate and multivariate regression analysis indicate that the examined meteorological factors statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) increased the concentration of ambient PM_{2.5}, with 30% of explainable variation in PM_{2.5} concentrations during examination period. In addition, impact of some meteorological factors on PM_{2.5} concentrations were different between season, as well as monitoring stations. The results of this investigation imply the importance of improving local meteorological conditions in order to improve air quality, as well as public health.

Introduction

As well as in the other part of world, in more than 25 cities in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Albania, North Macedonia, Montenegro and Serbia, annual concentrations of fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) exceeded air quality guidelines for PM_{2.5} suggested by World Health Organization (Colovic Daul M., et al, 2019). As numerous studies have shown that the presence of emitters is not the only factor that contributes to the mass concentrations of PM_{2.5} particles (Liu Y., et al, 2017), we wanted to investigate less researched and understandable association between meteorological factors and concentration of PM_{2.5} particles.

Methodology and Results

During 2017, with prospective study, designed as time series analysis, in the area of the City of Novi Sad, Serbia we provided daily data of PM_{2.5} particles from two monitoring stations (urban traffic and urban background), and meteorological parameters (air temperature (AT), relative humidity (RH) and wind speed (WS)), as well. Daily mass concentrations of PM_{2.5} particles were determined according to the prescribed standard method SRPS EN 12341:2015, while meteorological data was provided by Republic of Hydrometeorology Service of Serbia. We used ANOVA to determine the season variation of PM_{2.5} particles, Pearson coefficient to analyse correlation between PM_{2.5} and meteorological parameters, and univariate and multivariate regression analysis for possibility of local impact of meteorological parameters on mass concentration of PM_{2.5} particles. For the area of Novi Sad during the entire study period it is revealed a statistically significant negative relationship between AT and RH ($p < 0.01$), AT and PM_{2.5} ($p < 0.01$), WS and PM_{2.5} ($p < 0.05$) (Table 1), while a statistically significant positive correlation was found between the RH and WS ($p < 0.05$), and RH and PM_{2.5}, as well ($p < 0.05$). Using multiple linear regression (Table 2), it is estimated that higher concentrations of particles are expected during the day with lower daily AT ($\beta = -0.678$; $p < 0.01$) and reduced WS ($\beta = -0.678$; $p < 0.01$). During whole period, about 30% of daily variations in PM_{2.5} concentration were explained by variations in daily AT ($\beta = -0.678$; $p < 0.01$) and WS ($\beta = -0.678$; $p < 0.01$). In addition, impact of some meteorological factors on PM_{2.5} concentrations were different between season, as well as monitoring stations.

Conclusions

In the area of the City of Novi Sad, meteorological conditions represent one of the significant factors, beside emissions sources, that contribute to the ambient PM_{2.5} particles concentration. The results of this investigation imply the importance of improving local meteorological conditions in order to improve air quality, as well as public health.

References

Colovic Daul M., Kryzanowski M., Kujundzic O., 2019. Air Pollution and Human Health: The Case of the Western Balkans. Liu Y., Zhao N, Vanos J.K., Cao G, 2017. Effects of synoptic weather on ground-level PM_{2.5} concentrations in the United States. Atmos Environ 148, 297–305.

Table 1. Correlation between meteorological parameters and PM_{2.5} particles in Novi Sad during the 2017

	Air Temperature	Relative humidity	Wind speed	PM _{2.5}
Air Temperature	1			
Relative humidity	-0,798**	1		
Wind speed	-0,136	0,162*	1	
PM _{2.5}	-0,464**	0,208**	-0,202*	1

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$

Table 2. Regression analysis of the relationship between meteorological parameters and average daily concentrations of PM_{2.5} particles in Novi Sad during 2017

Variable	Univariate regression		Multivariate regression		R ²
	β	p value	β	p value	
Air Temperature (°C)*	-0,678	<0,01	-0,731	<0,01	
Relative humidity (%)	0,179	<0,01	-	-	0,286
Wind Speed (km/h)*	-2,302	<0,05	-3,077	<0,01	

* Included in multivariate regression; β - beta regression coefficient; R² - coefficient of determination of multivariate regression